

203 (218-CH₃), 189 (double hydrogen transfer from retro Diels-Alder fragment to form a highly conjugated allylic cation); NMR. (δ) 0.85-1.62 (methyl and methylene protons), 1.89 (vinyl-methyl protons), 2.35 (α-keto methylene at 2-position), broad m centered at 5.23 (proton at 12 position); λ_{max} 217 mμ; oxime m.p. 260°; LiAlH₄ reduction product m.p. 195°. All these data showed the presence of β-amyrone which was further confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

Second fraction was a mixture of triacontanol m.p. 80° and taraxerol m.p. 268°. Third fraction was β-amyrin m.p. 198° and the last one was β-sitosterol m.p. 135°. Each of them was identified through melting point, rotation, co-tlc and thorough spectral studies as described earlier¹. Other plants are analysed as before and the results of investigation of four investigated genera of family *Rhizophoraceae* are tabulated below.

TABLE 1.
Compound isolated (in gms)

Plant/source	Portion	Compound isolated (in gms)							
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
<i>R. conjugata</i> (Sundarban)	Leaves 1.5 Kg	0.05	0.50	x	0.70	x	x	0.01	0.10
<i>B. gymnorhiza</i> (Sundarban)	Leaves 3 Kg	5.00	x	x	6.00	x	x	1.00	0.70
<i>K. rheedi</i> (Sundarban)	Bark 2 Kg	1.00	x	0.02	t	x	x	0.04	x
	Leaves 1½ Kg	0.85	x	0.02	0.02	x	x	0.03	x
<i>C. roxburghiana</i> (Sundarban)	Bark 5 Kg	t	x	x	0.02	t	t	t	0.02
	Leaves 1.5 Kg	0.30	x	x	0.15	0.08	0.10	0.08	0.02

A=β-amyrin; B=β-amyrone; C=Friedelin; D=Taraxerol; E=Betulin; F=Betulinic acid; G=β-sitosterol; H=Triacontanol, t=traces by tlc.

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Thermodynamic Stability Constants of Praseodymium(III), Neodymium(III) and Samarium(III) with Tyrosine.

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Though there is a considerable information about formation constants of metal complexes of amino acids¹⁻⁴, little work appears to have been reported with tyrosine, a biological important molecule. In a previous communication^{5,7}, formation constants of lanthanons with tyrosine have been reported. In this note, thermodynamic stability constants of Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺ and Sm³⁺ with tyrosine are being reported.

Experimental

The protonation constant and successive formation constants were determined by Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁸⁻¹⁰. All chemicals used were either BDH or Aldrich AnalaR quality. The ligand solution was prepared in CO₂ free conductivity water immediately before use. The metal nitrate solutions were standardised by E.D.T.A. method. The thermostat bath temperature was maintained at 30° ± 0.1°. The mole ratio of metal to ligand was kept 1:5 in order to fulfil 'maximum coordination number of the metal. The three solutions (total volume 50 ml in each case) were prepared as follows:

A: 1.0 x 10⁻² M HNO₃

B: 1.0 x 10⁻² M HNO₃ + 0.25 x 10⁻² M ligand

C: 1.0 x 10⁻² M HNO₃ + 0.25 x 10⁻² M ligand + 0.5 x 10⁻² M metal nitrate.

An appropriate quantity of KNO₃ (1.0M) was added to maintain an ionic strength at 0.1, 0.2 or 0.3 M. The above solution, was titrated against carbonate free 0.1 M KOH solution. pH was measured on Photovolt digital pH meter having a sensitivity of 0.002 units.

The plots of pH versus the volume of alkali added were plotted. In calculations, concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titration. The calculated error in stability constant is ±0.01 log K units. The shape of curves were as usual.

Results and Discussion

The proton ligand curve was obtained by plotting degree of formation (α_{H}) of the proton complex against pH value using the relationship derived by Irving and Rossotti⁹⁻¹⁰. The proton ligand stability constant (amino functional group)

$\log K_1^H$ was obtained as Bjerrum half integral value method⁷. The same has been calculated by pointwise calculation method, at different points using the following equation :

$$\log P_{K_1}^H = pH + \log \frac{H\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}_H}$$

The complex ligand formation curve was then obtained by plotting degree of formation of the complex (\bar{n}) against negative logarithm of the concentration of non-protonated ligand (pL) using the relationship derived by Irving and Rossotti¹⁰. For the determination of metal-ligand stability constants, Bjerrum half integral method was used. In addition, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were obtained by pointwise calculation method using the following equations :

$$\log K_1 = pL - \log \frac{1-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}}$$

$$\log K_2 = pL - \log \frac{2-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}-1}$$

The value of \bar{n} obtained are of the order 2 between pH range 6.5-8.0. This suggests that Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} and Sm^{3+} form two types of complexes in the proportion 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 with tyrosine (Table 1).

Table. 1. VALUES OF THE PROTONATION CONSTANT and STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES AT 3^oS.

Cation	Constants	$\mu = 0.1$	$\mu = 0.2$	$\mu = 0.3$
	$\log K_1^H$ (amino functional group)	9.20	9.18	9.15
Pr^{3+}	$\log K_1$	4.68	4.60	4.53
	$\log K_2$	4.12	4.10	4.09
	$\log \beta_2$	8.80	8.71	8.62
Nd^{3+}	$\log K_1$	4.54	4.47	4.40
	$\log K_2$	4.01	3.96	3.91
	$\log \beta_2$	8.55	8.43	8.31
Sm^{3+}	$\log K_1$	4.91	4.85	4.79
	$\log K_2$	4.38	4.30	4.22
	$\log \beta_2$	9.29	9.15	9.01

Most of the amino acids are present as single protonated form HL in the pH range 2.7 to 8.5. A few amino acids occur as H_2L , H_2L^+ form over the whole range. This is true for tyrosine where protons of phenolic group are not released. The comparison of metal-ligand stability constant values of tyrosine with those of serine permits the conclusion that unionised hydroxyl group is not participating in complex formation^{8,11}. The coordination appears to be only through amino nitrogen and carboxylic oxygen. The difference in $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ for Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} and Sm^{3+} with tyrosine is less than 1.5, indicating the simultaneous formation of two types of complexes. The values of log step formation constant at various ionic strengths, extrapolated to zero ionic strength gave step thermodynamic formation constants¹⁰. Likewise the values of overall

thermodynamic stability were obtained and symbolised as experimental $\log \beta_2^{\mu=0}$ (Table-2). The values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ decreases with an increase in ionic strength¹². The order of overall stability of these complexes is $Sm^{3+} > Nd^{3+} > Pr^{3+}$ as expected from their electronic configuration.

Table 2. VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC STABILITY CONSTANTS

	Pr^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	Sm^{3+}
$\log K_1^{\mu=0}$	4.75	4.61	4.97
$\log K_2^{\mu=0}$	4.14	4.16	4.44
$\log \beta_2^{\mu=0}$ (experimental)	8.89	8.77	9.42

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Amine Exchange Reactions of Mixed Imine Schiff base Complexes of Ni(II)

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The amine exchange (transamination) reactions of coordinated salicylideneamine have been investigated by several workers earlier¹⁻⁸. The influence of basicity and concentration⁴⁻⁶ of the amine in the case of transamination reactions have been variously discussed, but no generalization is possible. The preparations of mixed ligand complexes of the type MLL' [Where L=salicylideneamine or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethylethylamine, L' =1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneamine and M=Ni(II)], have been reported earlier⁹⁻¹⁰. In the present investigation, the amine exchange reactions on above complexes have been carried out and the structures of the complexes have been discussed on the basis of experimental data.